

Influence of Brand Ambassador Endorsement on Lush Relaxer among Consumers in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The researcher investigated the influence of brand ambassador endorsement on consumer purchase behaviour towards Lush relaxer. The study aimed at evaluating consumers' exposure, channel of exposure, perception and factors that motivate their purchase decision. The research was anchored on the social influence theory and the source credibility theory. The survey research design was employed, utilising questionnaire for data collection. Findings indicated that a considerable proportion of consumers were cognizant of brand ambassador endorsed advertisements, which were found to enhance the patronage of Lush relaxer. The researcher pinpointed several motivating factors affecting the impact of these advertisements, including trust and credibility, relatability, authenticity and social proof. In conclusion, the researcher posited that the influence of brand ambassador's endorsement on consumer purchase behaviour towards Lush relaxer is a significant factor in driving sales and brand loyalty. Recommendations included urging manufacturer of Lush relaxer to leverage the power of brand ambassadors in their marketing strategy to continue to grow their customer base and achieve success in the competitive beauty industry.

Keywords: Advertising, Consumer Behaviour Brand Ambassadors, Celebrities, Attitude

Introduction

The rise of brand ambassador endorsements has become one of the most significant developments in the media landscape. Brand ambassadors are individuals who are hired by companies to represent their brand and promote their products or services. It is a marketing strategy used in promoting sales. Lake (2016); Asemah, Kente & Nkwam-Uwaoma (2020) and Asemah, Nkwam-Uwaoma & Amah (2023) see marketing as the process of telling consumers why they should choose your product or service over your competitors, therefore, marketing strategy is a detailed guide developed by a company or an organisation to achieve its goals and objectives.

In the past, brand ambassadors were often limited to a specific market or region. However, in this global age, brand ambassador endorsements have become a powerful tool for brands to reach a global audience and build a strong brand identity. Asemah, Kente, Nkwa-Uwaoma & Amah (2021) note that products, services and ideas are sold through businesses that are differentiated by their brand identities. Brand identity is communicated to the public via advertising. Brand ambassador endorsements have the

ability to create a sense of trust and credibility among consumers. When a popular celebrity or influencer promotes a product, it lends an air of authenticity and legitimacy to the brand. Consumers are more likely to trust the recommendation of someone they admire, making brand ambassador endorsements a powerful marketing tool in the global marketplace. Brand ambassadors also have the potential to create a lasting relationship between the brand and the consumer. By aligning with influencers who share the values and interests of their target audience, brands can create a sense of loyalty and connection that goes beyond a one-time endorsement. This can lead to long-term brand loyalty and repeat business, ultimately driving sales and revenue for the brand.

These endorsements can take many forms, including sponsored social media posts, television commercials and appearances at events. By associating their image with a particular brand, ambassadors can help to create positive associations and enhance the brand's reputation among consumers.

Brand ambassador endorsements can help to differentiate a brand from its competitors and create a unique selling proposition. By aligning themselves with a well-known celebrity or influencer, brands can stand out in a crowded marketplace and capture the attention of consumers who may be bombarded with advertising messages on a daily basis. Keller & Aaker (1998) note that brand ambassadors can help to enhance brand image and create positive associations with the brand. Asemah (2022); Asemah *et al* (2020); Asemah *et al* (2021); Asemah *et al* (2023) and Asemah *et al* (2023) note that brand image helps the consumers to choose which brand is a superior choice for them and they are compelled to make purchase expectations. When consumers see a brand ambassador endorsing a product, they are more likely to associate the product with the qualities and attributes of the ambassador. For example, if a consumer sees Mercy Johnson endorsing a hair relaxer product, they may assume that the product will help them achieve the same level of smooth and silky hair as hers.

Brand ambassadors can also influence consumer purchase behaviour through their ability to create a sense of social proof. Social proof is a psychological phenomenon where people look to the actions and behaviours of others to determine what is appropriate or desirable. When a consumer sees a brand ambassador endorsing a product, they are more likely to believe that the product is popular and in demand and it may also improve brand loyalty. Asemah & Nwammuo (2015) note brand loyalty is the basic tool for any company to survive in a severe competition; brand helps in creating relationship between consumer and producer. Brand loyalty is a fertile relationship concept and it is more than just a repeat purchase (Fournier, 1998).

According to Okpanachi, Ezeji & Asemah (2017), no business can survive without a reliable stream of customers. Therefore, consumer behaviour is the study of how individual customers, groups or organisations select, buy, use, and dispose of ideas, goods, and services to satisfy their needs and wants. It refers to the actions of the consumers in the marketplace and the underlying motives for those actions (Smriti Chand, 2018). By understanding what causes the consumers to buy particular goods and services,

they will be able to determine which products are needed in the marketplace, which are obsolete, and how best to present the goods to the consumers.

Statement of the Problem

Using brand ambassadors in advertising can be a powerful marketing strategy, but it also comes with its fair share of complex and complicated issues that need to be navigated carefully. Owusu-Kyei, Kong, Owusu-Akomeah & Afriyie (2023) researched the effects of celebrity endorsement on brand promotion in Ghana, opines that consumers views thousands of advertisement a day, but the ability to remember the ones that aligns with their needs is challenging. Therefore, advertisers must go extra mile to make sure consumers retain their adverts in their minds. One of the most significant challenges is ensuring that the brand ambassador aligns with the values, image and messaging of the brand. If there is a disconnect between the brand's identity and that of the ambassador, it can lead to confusion among consumers and damage the brand's reputation.

Another challenge in using brand ambassadors is measuring the effectiveness of the advertising campaign. Kuswandi, Kuriniadi & Hundura (2024) in a study on side effects of brand ambassadors on brands note that measuring purchase intension can be very difficult, because customers are dynamic in nature and they possess some concrete behaviours that might be difficult to understand and interpret.

Using brand ambassadors in advertising presents a multitude of complex and complicated issues that brands must navigate carefully. From aligning with brand values to selecting the right ambassador, managing ambassador behaviour, measuring effectiveness, and staying abreast of industry trends, brands must carefully consider these challenges to maximise the success of their advertising campaigns. This study was, therefore, motivated by the need to determine the influence of brand ambassadors' endorsement of lush relaxer on consumers in Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were to:

1. Examine the extent of exposure to Lush relaxer brand ambassadors' endorsement advertisements among consumers in Benin City.
2. Investigate the channels through which consumers are exposed to Lush Relaxer advertisements featuring brand ambassadors.
3. Assess consumers' perceptions of Lush Relaxer advertisements featuring brand ambassadors.
4. Determine the influence of brand ambassadors' endorsement on consumer purchase behaviour towards Lush Relaxer.

Overview of Advertising

Advertising is a pervasive and influential aspect of modern society. It is a powerful tool used by businesses to promote their products or services and persuade consumers to make purchases. In today's digital age, advertising has become even more prevalent, with messages reaching consumers through various channels such as television, radio, print media, social media, and online platforms.

Advertising is defined as a form of communication used by businesses to promote their products or services. It is a marketing strategy that aims to attract and persuade consumers to purchase a particular product or service. Arens (1992) notes that "advertising is the sharing of information in non-personal way typically paid for in convince manner about products and services by a specific sponsor through certain media." Richards & Curran (2002) see advertisement as a paid form of communication from an identifiable source and designed to persuade the receiver to take some action now or in the future." Similarly, Janoschka (2004) argued that advertising is a paid-form of non-personal communication about an organisation and its products that is transmitted to a target audience through a mass medium such as television, radio, newspapers, magazines, direct mail, public transport, outdoor displays or catalogues. Furthermore, Frolova (2014) described the basic roots of advertisement and presumed that advertising is the paid-form of impersonal communication to spread business information about the company products and services through various communication channels by an identified sponsor and clarified the basic elements of advertisement such as "paid form of communication, the presence of identified sponsor, distribution through the media, the presence of a specific audience for treatment, lack of personalisation of distributed information and aimed action." The purpose of advertising is to create awareness, generate interest, and ultimately drive sales.

Brand Ambassador: An Overview

A brand ambassador is a person who represents and advertises a company, supports its offers and acts as the embodiment of the company's corporate identity through words and actions. Brand ambassadors are experts when it comes to talking about the brand online and offline. But it can also be your own employees within the company. Brand ambassadors do not need fixed qualifications. Rogers & Cartao (1962) see a brand ambassador as an opinion leader who is able to influence other individuals, opinion and behaviour. Brand ambassador is a mediator between internal and external brand management and can have a significant impact on customer perception of brands and organisations and in general, the brand ambassador are brand representatives who confirm brands by their reputation (Goutam, 2013; Harris & De Cheratony, 2001).

A brand ambassador is a tool that is used by the company to communicate with the public to improve their sales number. Fisher-Buttinger & Vallaster (2008) note that a brand ambassador is a person who acts in support and on behalf of a particular brand. A brand ambassador is a person who supports a brand from a popular public figure (Dewi,

Edyanto & Siagian, 2020). A brand ambassador is an influential figure who plays a crucial role in promoting a brand and various elements within it to achieve business goals. A brand ambassador is a brand representative responsible for elevating the image and increasing the visibility and popularity of a brand.

Consumer Purchase Behaviour

Consumer purchase behaviour is a complex phenomenon that is influenced by a variety of factors including personal preferences, societal norms, marketing strategies and economic conditions. Understanding consumer purchase behaviour is essential for businesses to effectively target and attract customers. Consumer behaviour can be influenced by both internal and external stimuli. Some of the most common stimuli are personal factors, cultural factors and social factors as mentioned as above. Consumer's factors such as perception, motivation, learning and memory comprise influence how the consumer responds to the marketing stimuli. (Kotler & Keller, 2007). Every individual's consumer behaviour or purchase decision can significantly be influenced by their buying habits which are affected by technological, political, demographic, cultural, economic, personal, psychological, and social factors, et cetera. These factors are revealed or shown in the attitude, drive, perception, disposition, knowledge, and lifestyle of the consumers.

One key aspect of consumer purchase behaviour is the decision-making process. Consumers go through a series of steps including problem recognition, information search, evaluation of alternatives, purchase decision, and post-purchase evaluation. Each of these steps can be influenced by external factors such as advertising, word-of-mouth reviews, and in-store displays. Consumers have unique preferences for products, brands, and shopping experiences. These preferences are shaped by personal values, experiences and perceptions of the world around them. Brand ambassador endorsement influences the behaviour of consumers to buy a specific product through cognition.

Empirical Review

Elijah & Apeh (2023) studied celebrity and testimonial advertising on Lush and Darling hair products. The objectives of the study were to ascertain the extent to which celebrity and testimonial advertisements influence the interest and recall of the buyer towards Lush and Darling hair products and to determine the extent to which celebrity and testifier credibility shape the conviction of consumers and buying intention of Lush and Darling hair products. The frameworks of the study are reference group theory and source credibility theory. The study adopted survey research design with a sample size of 384. The research data showed that majority of the respondents claimed that the celebrity and testimonial advertisements make them remember and influence their interest in the Lush and Darling hair products. The findings showed further that respondents also claimed that the credibility of celebrities and testifiers used in adverting Lush and Darling hair products shaped their conviction and intention to buy. The study recommended aggressive implementation of the use of celebrities in the advertisements of their products.

The similarities include the use of survey research design and the assessment of buyer behaviour. Meanwhile, the differences include, the use of interview, framework and the elaborate look into brand ambassador as a concept which includes celebrity endorsement, athletes etc.

Ogunyombo, Azeez & Oyero (2017) did a study on the influence of social media advertisements on purchase decisions of undergraduates in three Nigerian universities. The study examined the exposure, viewership and influence of social media advertisements on the purchasing decision. Key findings showed that social media advertisements are very visible in terms of high exposure, but limited in influencing purchase decision among the respondents. Respondents agreed to viewing the advertisement, but did not really pay much attention to the content of the message which in turn, made it ineffective. In contrast to the current study, Ogunyombo *et al* (2017) focused on how social media advertisements can be used to influence consumer behaviour towards purchasing a product, while both studies are concerned with influencing consumer purchase decision, Ogunyombo *et al* (2017) concentrated on the level of viewership an advertising has on social media, rather than the significance of the message on the viewers.

Gauns, Pillai, Kamat, Chen & Chang (2017) carried out a study on the impact of celebrity endorsement on consumer buying behaviour in the State of Goa. The researchers adopted survey research design with structured questionnaire which was administered to 200 consumers from June 2015 to April 2016. The findings showed that a significant association exists between celebrity supporters/neutral/opposers and gender, age, occupation and income level, except in education and location. Finding also revealed that consumers consider celebrity endorsements more attractive and influential than non-celebrity endorsements. The celebrity attributes tested in this study showed positive relationship with purchase intention, except in expertise and trustworthiness of celebrity. These scholars therefore, concluded that celebrity attributes impact the purchase intention of consumers. In terms of methodology, this study is in alignment with the current study but differs in scope. While this study examined 200 respondent in Goa, the current study examines 400 respondent in Nigeria.

In a review conducted by Ismailla & Oziohu (2021) on brand ambassador and consumer patronage of FMCGS mediating effect of advertisement believability. It was noted that brand ambassador has an insignificant direct effect on consumer patronage and advertisement believability has no mediating effect on the influence of brand ambassador on customer patronage. The researcher used a questionnaire to elicit information from respondent and recommends that managers of FMCGS should use a hybrid model of a brand ambassador and behavioural advertising to elicit the desired patronage from their target customers. The findings show that advertisement believability has a significant effect on customer patronage.

This study shares similarities with the present research on the influence of brand ambassador on consumer purchase behaviour, as both investigate how brand ambassador

can enhance consumer decision towards a product; while Ismaila & Oziohu (2021) focused on advertisement believability, the current study focuses on consumer purchase behaviour towards Lush relaxer.

Theoretical Framework

Social Influence Theory

The theory was proposed and developed by psychologist Kurt Lewin in the 1940s. Lewin was a seminal figure in the field of social psychology and is widely recognised for his contributions to understanding group dynamics, social behaviour and human motivation. He introduced the concept of social influence to explain how individuals are influenced by the actions, opinions, and norms of the groups to which they belong. Lewin's work laid the foundation for later research in social psychology and has had a lasting impact on the study of human behaviour in social contexts. Brand ambassadors, who are often seen as popular and credible sources of information, can leverage their social influence to shape consumer perceptions and preferences, leading to increased purchase behaviour among their followers. One of the key concepts within social influence theory is conformity, which refers to the tendency of individuals to adjust their beliefs, attitudes, and behaviours to align with those of the group. Conformity can be driven by a desire to fit in, gain social approval, or avoid rejection, and it often involves a process of informational influence, where individuals look to the group for guidance on how to think and act. Social influence theory encompasses the concept of persuasion, which involves the deliberate attempt to change someone's beliefs, attitudes, or behaviours through the use of persuasive tactics such as arguments, appeals to emotion or social influence.

Source Credibility Theory

Source credibility theory, also known as credibility theory, is a communication theory that focuses on how the perceived credibility of a message source can influence the acceptance and effectiveness of the message. It was first introduced in the 20th century in response to the growing importance of credibility in communication and persuasion. The theory refers to the perceived trustworthiness, competence and goodwill of a person or entity. It is a powerful form of social influence where individuals are more likely to follow or believe information from credible sources compared to less credible ones.

The theory seeks to explain how individuals perceive the credibility of sources of information and how this perception influences their attitudes and behaviours. The theory has implications for understanding persuasion, attitude change and information processing in communication contexts. The theory identifies three key factors that contribute to source credibility as expertise, trustworthiness and likability. These factors play a crucial role in shaping individuals' attitudes and behaviours in response to persuasive messages. One of the primary criticisms of the source credibility theory

revolves around its simplistic view of credibility and its failure to capture the complexities of human judgment and decision-making processes.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The design was selected in order to get the opinions of respondents on the subject matter. The survey included a series of questions designed to collect information from respondents. The questionnaire was close-ended, using the 5-rating likert scale format. The term "population of study" refers to the entire group of individuals or elements that the researcher is interested in studying and drawing conclusion about (Asemah & Nwaoboli, 2024; Asemah, Gujbawu, Ekharefo & Okpanachi, 2012). The population of this study comprises female residents in Benin City (between the ages of twenty and sixty). Based on the population projection by the National Population Commission, the female population in Benin is three hundred and forty thousand, two hundred and eighty (340,280). These select population no doubt is the major user of the product.

A sample size of 400 respondents was taken for the study from the populations of the study. The sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane sample size determination formula. Purposive sampling and random sampling technique were utilised for this study. The questionnaire was used for the study.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1: Extent of Exposure to Lush Relaxer Advertisement Featuring Brand Ambassadors

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Very high	197	51.7
High	163	42.8
Can't tell	17	4.5
Low	4	1.0
Very Low	0	0
Total	381	100

The table above showed that a significant number of respondents are exposed to Lush relaxer advertisements endorsed by a brand ambassador.

Table 2: Channel(s) of Exposure to Lush Relaxer Advertisement Endorsed by Brand Ambassadors.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Television	122	32.0

Newspaper	34	8.9
Magazine	11	2.9
Indigenous media	21	5.5
Social media	193	50.7
Total	381	100

The table above showed the channels through which respondents are exposed to Lush relaxer advertisement featuring a brand ambassador. The data show that advertisers of Lush Relaxer use different channels to reach out to their potential customers.

Table 3: Brand Ambassadors Influence my Decision of Purchasing Lush Relaxer

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly agree	173	45.4
Agree	179	47.0
Neutral	29	7.6
Disagree	0	0
Strongly disagree	0	0
Total	381	100

Table 3 revealed that the use of brand ambassadors in advertisements influences consumers' purchase decision because it makes the advertisement more appealing.

Table 4: Factor(s) that Motivate me to Purchase a Product Endorsed by Brand Ambassadors

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Trust and credibility	109	28.6
Relatability	57	15.0
Expertise and authority	71	18.6
Emotional connection	54	14.2
Authenticity and social proof	90	23.6
Total	381	100

Table 4 demonstrated the various factors that influence consumers' purchase behaviour. Respondents claimed that these factors are pivotal in making purchase decision. This suggests that advertisers should look out for these factors when selecting ambassadors for their product.

Discussion of Findings

Findings revealed that a significant portion of the respondents had been exposed to Lush Relaxer advertisements featuring brand ambassadors. This indicates that the brand

ambassador endorsement strategy employed by Lush Relaxer is effectively reaching consumers and creating awareness about the product. The exposure to brand ambassadors helps in creating a connection between the consumer and the product, as consumers may relate to or be inspired by the brand ambassadors, leading to a positive perception of the brand and product. The findings align with previous researches by Elijah & Apeh (2023); Ogunyombo *et al* (2017); Ajayi, Oyedokun & Chigbo (2023) and Aldajani & Daajani (2019), which emphasised that exposure to brand ambassador endorsed advertisement inspire their interest in the product. The ability of brand ambassadors to captivate their attention is essential in today's dynamic marketplace where various products vie for the attention of potential consumers.

The research also revealed that a significant number of respondents have seen on television, billboards, social media platforms or posters during direct selling at market places. This finding highlights the role of visual marketing in shaping perceptions and creating a favourable image of Lush relaxer. The studies by Anusree (2024); Ogunyombo *et al* (2017) and Akpan, Nwankpa & Agu (2015) align with this study on the effectiveness of various channels in advertiser.

Furthermore, the research findings indicated that consumers perceived Lush relaxer advertisements featuring brand ambassadors as more credible and trustworthy compared to traditional advertisements. Some of the factors that motivated them to purchase the product include: trust and credibility, authenticity, expertise, relatability and emotional connection. Other factors that may discourage them include lack of authenticity, overexposure and misalignment with personal values. This study is in agreement with the studies conducted by Malik & Qureshi (2016); Elijah & Apeh (2023) and Dewi, Edyanto & Siagian (2020), which revealed that celebrity advertisement shapes consumers' perception and interest in a product. The higher the positive perception of the consumer towards brand ambassador, the higher the purchase decision and brand awareness or image.

The findings of the study showed that brand ambassador influence consumers' purchase decision in different ways which include: boost in credibility and trust, influence purchase intention, emotional connection and engagement, enhanced brand image and ultimately drove purchase behaviour. The study by Dewi, Edyanto & Siagian (2020) is in alignment with this study which revealed that brand ambassador has a significant effect on brand image and the purchase decision. The endorsement served as a form of social proof, reassuring consumers of the product's reliability and authenticity, ultimately influencing their purchase decisions.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher concluded that there is a high level of exposure to brand ambassador endorsed advertisement of Lush relaxer among respondents and that the endorsement has a significant influence on their purchase behaviour. Furthermore, a substantial percentage of respondents expressed that brand

ambassadors attract them to the product, emphasising the role of visually compelling marketing in shaping positive perceptions. Thus, manufacturer of Lush relaxer should conduct market research to identify the most effective brand ambassadors for Lush relaxer who align with the brand's values and target audience instead of using multiple ambassadors, for easy recall and also design an effective strategy to increase the level of awareness of the brand. Also, advertisers should focus on authenticity and transparency in brand ambassador endorsements to build a strong emotional connection with consumers. Additionally, advertisers should continuously adapt and evolve the brand ambassador strategy based on consumer feedback and market trends to stay relevant and competitive in the industry. There is need to constantly measure the impact of brand ambassador endorsements on consumer behaviour through surveys and sales data to evaluate the effectiveness of the strategy.

References

- Ajayi, M.P., Oyedokun, D.M. & Chigbo, D.C. (2023). Influence of Instagram advertising of Mega Growth hair products on the purchasing behaviour of female undergraduate students of Chrisland University, Abeokuta, Nigeria. *Journal of Mass Communication*, 10 (1), 41-82.
- Anussree, P. (2024). A study on Influence of Celebrity-endorsed advertising on purchasing behaviour among college students. *International Journal of Trends in Scientific Research and Development*, 8 (3), 678-681
- Asemah, E. S., Nkwam- Uwaoma, A. O. & Safina, S.(2023). *Research and tactics in public relations and advertising*. Jos: Jos University Press.
- Asemah, E.S., Nkwam-Uwaoma, A.O. & Amah, F. O. (2023). *Notes on integrated marketing communication*. Jos University Press.
- Asemah, E.S., Akase, M.T. & Nkwam-Uwaoma, A.O. (2023). *Business of international public relations and advertising (2nd ed.)*. Jos: University Press.
- Asemah, E.S. (2022) *Perspectives on advertising and public relations (4th ed.)*. Jos: Lizborn Press.
- Asemah, E.S., Kente, J.S. & Nkwam-Uwaoma, A.O. (2020). *Marketing foundation for advertising and public relations*. Jos: University Press.
- Asemah, E.S., Kente, J.S., Nkwam-Uwaoma, A.O. & Amah, F.O. (2021). *Contemporary issues in advertising and public relations*. Jos: Matkol Press.
- Asemah, E. S., Okpanachi, R. A. & Edegoh, L. O. N. (2013). Business advantages of corporate social responsibility practice: A critical review. *Journal of New Media and Mass Communication*, 18, 45-54.
- Asemah, E.S., Edegbohs, L.O.N. & Anatusi, C. (2012). Corporate social responsibility and community relations as critical factors in conflict management, *Maiduguri Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 10 (1), 47-55.
- Asemah, E. S. & Okpanachi, R. A. (2014). Determinants of brand loyalty among residents of Jos, Nigeria. *Zaria Journal of Communication*, 4, 19-28.
- Bovee, C.L. & Arens, W. F. (1992). *Contemporary advertising*, Boston: Richard D. Irwin, Inc.

- Dewi, L.G., Edyanto, N. & Siagian, H. (2020). The effect of brand ambassador, brand image, and brand awareness on purchase decision of Pantene Shampoo in Surabaya, Indonesia. SHS web conference 76, 01023. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1051/Shscconf/20207601023>
- Dominick, J. (2013). *The dynamics of mass communication*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Ekwueme, A. C. & Okoro, N. (2018). Analysis of the use of social media advertising among selected online businesses in Nigeria. *International Journal of International Relations, Media and Mass Communication Studies*, 4(2) .28-43
- Elijah, E.O. & Apeh, A. (2023) Celebrity testimonial advertising of Lush and Darling hair products: the anatomy of influences and buyer behaviour. *ESUT Journal of Media Studies*, (14), 1-14.
- Erdogan, B. Z. (1999). Celebrity endorsement: A literature review. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 15(4), 291–314.
- Fisher-Buttinger, C. & Vallaster, C. (2008). Brand ambassadors: strategic diplomats or tactical promoters? Metaphors and metamorphosis. Retrieved from https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1057/9780230227538_9
- Fournier, S.M. (1998). Consumers and their brands: Developing relationships theory in consumer research. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 24(4), 343-373.
- Goutam, D. 2013. Influence of brand ambassadors on buying behaviour of soft drinks: With reference to belgaum city. *IMPACT: International Journal of Research in Business Management*, 1, 9-18.
- Israel, O. & Oguche, E. N. (2018). Knowledge and perception of social media advertising among students of Kogi state university, Anyigba. *Global Media Journal*, 16, 1-8.
- Kotler, P. & Keller, K. (2007). *Marketing Management (13th ed.)*. Canada: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Karimova, G. Z. (2012). *Bakhtin and interactivity: A conceptual investigation of advertising communication*. USA, Palo Alto: Academica Press, LLC.
- Kuswandi, I.R., Kurniadi, B.A. & Hundura, R. (2024). Side effects of brand ambassadors on brands. *Ilomata International Journal of Management*, 5(1), 280-293.
- Janoschka, A. (2004). *Web advertising: New forms of communication on the internet*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Lake, L. (2016). *What is marketing? A beginner's guide to marketing*. Retrieved from <https://www.thebalance.com/what-is-marketng-2296057>.
- Liu, S.-F., Lee, H.-C. & Lien, N.-H. (2021). Do fast fashion consumers prefer foreign brands? The moderating roles of sensory perception and consumer personality on purchase intentions. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 26(2), 103-111.
- Lush Hair Africa, (2025). No-Lye relaxer super. Retrieved from <https://lushhaierafrica.com/product/no-lye-relaxer-super?>
- Malik, H.M. & Qureshi, M.M. (2016). The impact of celebrity endorsement on consumer buying behaviour. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*, 26, 66-79.
- Mayne, I. (2000). The inescapable images: Gender and advertising, *Equal Opportunities International*, 19 (2/3/4), 56-61.

- McCracken, G. (1987). Advertising: Meaning or information. *Advances in Consumer Research*, (14), 121-124.
- Nguyen, K., Minh, S.V., Nguyen, H.T. & Tran, N. (2023). The role of brand ambassadors in shaping brand image and driving purchase intentions: A case study in the fashion industry in Vietnam. *Kurdish Studies*, 11(02), 2761-2781.
- Okorie, N., Oyedepo, T. & Akhidenor, G. (2012). The dysfunctional and functional effect of celebrity endorsement on brand patronage. *Online Journal of Communication and Media Technologies*, 2(2), 141-152.
- Ogunyombo, O., Oyero, O., Azeez, K. (2017). Influence of social media advertisements on purchase decisions of undergraduates in three Nigerian universities. *Journal of Communication and Media Research*, 9(2), 244-255.
- Owusu-Kyei, M., Kong, Y., Owusu-Akomeah, M. & Afriyie, S.O. (2023). The effects of celebrity endorsements on brand promotion. *International Journal of research and Innovation in social science (IJRISS)*, 7(1), 23-35.
- Osifo, S., J. & Agbonifoh, B. A. (2018). Customer loyalty and unethical behaviour among salespersons in the Nigerian Banking Industry. *Nigerian Journal of Marketing*, 6(1), 24-35.
- Owusu-Mensah, S., Nimssah, W. K., & Mensah, N. O. (2013). The effect of brand name on customer loyalty in the mobile communication industry in Ghana. *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 1(3), 62-86.
- Putri, Z.A. & Hidayat, A.M. (2024) the influence of brand ambassador on impulse buying and brand trust as intervening on Azarine products through shopee E- commerce. *Journal of management and Economic studies*, 6 (1), 82-92.
- Rogers, E. M. & Cartano, D. G. (1962). Methods of measuring opinion leadership. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 435-441.
- Richards. J. I. & Curran, C. M. (2002). *Oracles on advertising: Searching for a definition*. *Journal of Advertising*, 31 (2), 63-76.
- Rehman, F.U., Javed, F., Nawaz, T., Ahmed, I. & Hyder, S. (2014). Some insights in the historical prospective of hierarchy of effects model: A short review. *Information Management and Business Review*, 6(6), 301-308.
- Samar, F. & Samreen, L. (2015). Impact of advertisement on buying behaviours of the consumers: Study of cosmetic industry in Karachi City. *International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research*, 3(2), 117-129.
- Safi, H., Azouri, M. & Azouri, A. (2018). The effect of celebrity endorsement on consumer behaviour: case of the Lebanese jewelry industry. *Arab Economic and Business journal*, 13 (2), 190-196.
- Tyagi, C.L. & Kumar, A. (2004). *Advertising Management*. New Delhi: Atlantic Publishers And Distributors.